

Literature research

The literature search on mortality rates was carried out in the search engine PubMed using the search terms "mortality", "patient care" and "long-term care" (text words and MESH terms). Hits on mortality related to COVID-19 were excluded by operator NOT. The result of the search yielded 62 publications, of which 4 publications reported mortality rates of people in need of care. Mortality rates were taken from reports showing structural, economic and social "closeness" to Germany (Bergland et al., 2017; Carey et al., 2008; Fried et al., 1998; Park et al., 2021). The values determined support the assumption that people in need of care die more frequently than other people in need of care, depending on their morbidity and social environment. A mortality rate for "those in need of care" vs. "those not in need of care" has not been reported in the literature to date. For this reason, two mortality rate ratios were used as extreme values to model the incidence in this study (Fried et al., 1998; Park et al., 2021) and used in a sensitivity analysis to calculate two scenarios (scenario 1 with a 3.2 -fold mortality rates (Fried et al., 1998) for the upper limit and Scenario 2 with a 1.17-fold mortality rate (Park et al., 2021) for the lower limit).